

Rapid Detection and control system for Antimicrobial Resistance

Public Procurement of Innovation

Addressing Europe's urgent need of a rapid detection and effective infection control system for antimicrobial resistance through the implementation of a value-based cross-border collaborative procurement of innovative solutions.

Co-funded by the COSME programme of the European Union

What is RaDAR?

The RaDAR project is a European Commission co-funded initiative which aims to **address the European urgent need of a rapid detection and effective infection control system for antimicrobial resistance (AMR)** through the implementation of a value-based **cross-border collaborative procurement of innovative solutions**.

The common identification of the needs by a cross-border group of 4 procurement organisations (from ES, FR and IT) will promote an increased impact of the adopted innovation and will **collaboratively give response to the current AMR problem affecting the European Union (EU)**.

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Why SMEs?

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the market, and specially SMEs, have demonstrated a great capacity to rapidly give response to the health and societal needs. Due to their intrinsic flexibility, adaptability, and capacity to develop technology and generate knowledge, **SMEs are currently playing a key role in the rapid and efficient development of innovative solutions to overcome the threat of AMR.** RaDAR will leverage from these advances to adopt innovative solutions that will:

- 1) Respond to the AMR increasing problem;
- 2) Provide SMEs access to public tenders/contracts;
- 3) Bring value to the health system and foster its digital transformation;
- 4) Contribute to decision making of public authorities in alignment with EU Health policies and European Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA);
- 5) Contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

*Despite the fact that both the program and the project are committed on SMEs, larger companies are, in the same way, welcome to participate.

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The Partners

RaDAR is composed of a cross-border Buyers Group composed of 4 public organisations from 3 different European countries (France, Spain and Italy) who work collaboratively to act as early adopters and **promote innovation, through the identification, evaluation and procurement of innovative solutions** that will address their common needs related to one of the most important challenges that are currently present in the political agenda in EU and worldwide.

Complementarily, a diverse and carefully selected supporting entities will ensure that the Buyers Group execute a procurement of innovative solutions that will meet both Consortium and individual needs.

Learn more about the Consortium [here](#).

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Prior Information Notice

The RaDAR Buyers Group ([RESAH](#), [ICO](#), [OSAK](#), and [UNINA- DISAP](#)) has have identified an unmet need for rapid detection and control systems to address antimicrobial resistance, and has published a [Prior Information Notice](#) (PIN) to publicise the project and **provide an opportunity for potential solution providers to express interest in the forthcoming open market consultation** and subsequent procurement.

This is an opportunity for potential solution providers, suppliers, and interest groups to express interest in following the project from its inception. **Expressions of interest are invited from all parts of the supply chain** to better understand the capacity, capability and appetite of the supply-chain to deliver demanded solutions. The data collected will be used solely by the RaDAR Consortium for the finalities of the project. RaDAR will not share your data with third parties for any purpose

Fill in the [expression of interest form](#) to stay updated on the project's developments.

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Contact Us

Get in touch by sending an email to contact@radar-ppi.com or visit the contact section of our [website](#).

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Legal Notice

The RaDAR PPI project has received funding from the COSME Programme of the European Union, Grant Agreement N° 101036228.

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